

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE CONCEPTS OF LANGUAGE AND THINKING IN THE ANALYSIS OF ARTISTIC TEXTS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION.

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Abstract: In this article, the scientific-theoretical basis of the analysis of artistic texts in primary classes in the modern education system is analyzed.

Keywords: Thinking, human, intuition, psychology, neurophysiology, cybernetics, mental practices, technical modeling, etc.

Thinking is the process of active reflection of objective reality in imagination, understanding and discussion, it is the ability of a person to think, and it is based on the knowledge, skills and concepts acquired in the process of thinking. It serves to understand its essence. It plays the main role in the accurate (adequate) and careful imagining of certain logical reality in the human mind. "By reflecting the general aspects of reality with the help of thinking, we can learn the essence of individual, concrete objects. In order to know something through thinking, it is necessary to create an understanding about it first. General laws and concepts are used to create an understanding of the subject in our mind. For example, we know that a water molecule is a complex chemical substance consisting of hydrogen and oxygen atoms. Here, we use the terms "complex chemical substance", "hydrogen" and other similar concepts to adapt the phenomenon to general laws.

Thinking and the process of thinking are studied in ways related to the theory of cognition, psychology and neurophysiology, as well as technical modeling of mental processes in cybernetics. Thinking can be individual (subjective) and social. and cannot live without thinking. In fact, the desired name, the name is a conditional symbol, it is optional and at the same time mandatory for the society. In this case, any object or feature can become a symbol of any object or event. For example, traffic lights perform a specific function. A red light means stop, the road is closed. But this does not mean that red means "stop". The color red itself has no innate, natural connection with the meaning of stopping. In us, red color has different ideas in people's minds - enthusiasm, blood, youth, love, etc. can tell. In addition, any color could be taken as a semaphore light meaning "stop", but in our society this color is used in this sense, it is socially agreed and mandatory for passengers. Here the voluntary

and social compulsion of connecting between the messenger and the message is clearly demonstrated.

It is necessary to mention again and again the emphasis on the close connection between thought and language. Thought occurs in the form of language, and language itself is thought. Obviously, none of us can imagine our ability to think without language - we think and think through language. From a biological point of view, a person is a thinking animal, that is, the ability to think separates a person from an animal. Thinking is expressed through language and words. Therefore, Mir Alisher:

Man is a very animal,

I know that there is no gem more precious than you.

they glorify the word so much.

The following explanation is given to the concept of "language" in OTIL: "A system of sounds, words and grammatical tools that serve as a tool for expressing ideas and communication." In this definition, the communicative function of the language is emphasized. In other sources, the abstract, generalized epistemological relationship of the language is also taken into account. , the problem of language and thinking is a very wide-ranging issue, which is a clear proof of the many studies that have been done.

There is no thinking without language. We cannot express our thoughts and concepts about the desired subject, event or event without language, at least without exclamations. As the objective reality is reflected in the human mind, it is determined by words, formed in words and placed and sealed in the most convenient way for easy finding and use at any time in the sections and sections of the language-consciousness treasury. For example, looking at the falling snow, compounds such as It is snowing or Snowing pass through our imagination. So, language units are not only "It's snowing." It is used to convey and transmit an idea, but also to reflect it in thinking, form its reception, and store it in memory. Our thinking is united with language to such an extent that there is no need to separate them, that is, to distinguish the processes of thinking and speaking, as well as the possibilities of internal speech, and to separate them from language. The education that a person receives until the last day of his life is amalgamated through words and language. That is why scientists distinguish between the educational and educational functions of language - the transmission of the product of human thought from generation to generation. In fact, we cannot imagine education without language. So, it is an important condition of the language learning process.

There is another aspect worth noting that language does not exist without thought. If we list the words that come to our mouths without thinking (for example: gadur, gadur, bubak, baban, etc.), it does not acquire any meaning for us, that is, it cannot create a specific concept or imagination. It even seems to be waving and waving. So it is neither a language nor a speech! That's why Alisher Navoi in his work "Muhokamatul lug'atayn" about 600 years ago said: "Alfoz ibarotdin murod manidur" is a short and clear statement that meaning is thought from language. A simple example can show that language and thinking are inseparable. When you remember the name of an acquaintance, you have a hard time naming him, you count all kinds of signs (gray-white, ash-faced, blue blouse, gold earring, etc.), but you still cannot express his name clearly until you remember it. Or, on the contrary, you easily read a word that you do not know the meaning of, but you do not understand its meaning. Similarly, reading a letter (or hearing a speech) in an unknown language (foreign, unfamiliar language). You can read, but you don't understand anything. For you, this language can neither influence your thinking nor perform the function of information transfer, expression of opinion, and progress. Therefore, this unfamiliar language can neither be a language nor a thought for you. That is why learning another language means learning the way of thinking of another people. In this work, Mir Alisher proved that language and thought are inseparable, but not the same thing, that each nation's way of thinking is unique and that this is reflected in its language by comparing the lexicon and grammatical system of Turkish and Persian languages. As the basis of the lexical and grammatical richness of the Turkish language, Mir Alisher sees the basis of "quicker comprehension and higher comprehension and a purer and purer nature than the Turkish variety", which can be seen by comparing the meanings and functions of hundreds of words and a number of grammatical forms that exist in the Turkish language and do not have their alternatives in the Persian language. proves with From this we are satisfied that language and thinking, although inseparable, are not the same thing. Language is a heritage of generations "ready from time immemorial" for every society, whose acceptance is general and mandatory. Members of society are naturally not interested in issues such as how the language appeared, who created it, who compiled it, and who created the symbols in it. In our daily life, we ask our teammates: "Why is this object named like that (for example, a book)?" no one asks that question. Society members are used to accepting the language "as it is". They are the inner nature of the symbols, their history, etc. does not need to be concerned with or

substitute one symbol for another. So, the relationship between language and thinking is a dialectical relationship and follows the laws of joint development. Therefore, these two phenomena in a dialectical relationship are an inseparable, mutually demanding complex whole, so the fields of science that study them are closely related, but not the same. The way of thinking is studied by the science of logic, and the language is studied by linguistics (linguistics). You will study each of these subjects separately.

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